

PRIMARY LESION OF GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN NON-HODGKIN'S LYMPHOMA**Capanji A.,***student, Faculty of General Medicine,
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Department of Hematology
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Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas are a group of malignant neoplasms arising from lymphoid tissue, mainly lymph nodes, and are the most common malignant neoplasms of the circulatory system in many countries, including the Republic of Moldova. In most cases, non-Hodgkin's lymphomas begin with lesions of the peripheral lymph nodes (nodal lymphomas), however, in recent years, the number of patients with primary extranodal non-Hodgkin's lymphomas has increased [1]. Features of clinical manifestations, methods of diagnosis and treatment were studied on the basis of data from 50 patients with non-Hodgkin's lymphomas with a primary lesion of the gastrointestinal tract, treated at the Oncological Institute, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova. The overall survival of patients in different stages of the disease was also studied.

Keywords: non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, extranodal lesion, gastrointestinal tract.

Introduction

The gastrointestinal tract is the most common primary localization for extranodal non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, accounting for 20 to 40% of all extranodal lymphomas. Approximately in 60-75% of cases, the primary focus occurs in the stomach, less often in the small intestine, caecum, colon and rectum [2]. Clinical and morphological studies have established that the most common type is gastric histiocytic lymphoma. This tumor occurs in 60% of cases and is currently classified as B-cell lymphoma, which is most common in the Middle East and the Mediterranean and in this sense has also been called "Mediterranean lymphoma" [3]. Most primary gastric lymphomas develop against the background of chronic gastritis. Moreover, other variants of extranodal lymphomas are also associated with chronic inflammatory processes. In 1993, evidence was presented that *H. pylori* plays an important role in the occurrence of a subgroup of gastric MALT lymphomas [4, 5]. Based on the study of all manifestations of NHL by oncohematologists, it was found that the most important factors for an unfavorable prognosis are: age over 60 years, general condition of the patient, stage III-IV of the disease, the presence of more than one extranodal lesion, bone marrow damage [6]. This formed the basis of the international prognostic index - IPI. According to the number of unfavorable prognostic factors, there are 4 risk groups for early progression of the disease:

- low - absence or presence of one unfavorable factor;
- low/medium - the presence of 2 factors;
- medium / high - the presence of 3 factors;
- high - the presence of 4 factors.

The presence of two or more factors negatively affects the prognosis of the disease, regardless of the morphological variant of the tumor, for example, in diffuse NHL with large B cells, the 5-year survival rate at low risk is 72%, at high risk - 22% [6, 7].

Materials and methods

The study included 50 patients with non-Hodgkin's lymphomas with a primary lesion of the gastrointestinal tract, who were treated in the Oncological Institute, Republic of Moldova, in the period from 1998 to 2021, aged 20 to 78 years (average age - 49 years). In all patients from the study group, the following were studied: age at diagnosis, gender, clinical dates, date and reason for visiting a doctor, date of confirmation of the diagnosis and the time interval from the start of disease to confirmation (duration of the disease before diagnosis), paraclinical dates, methods of treatment, efficacy and complications of treatment, overall survival. The definition of morphological variants of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas was carried out in accordance with the Classification of lymphoid neoplasms proposed by the World Health Organization in 2016. The clinical stage of the disease was established according to the International Clinical Classification adopted in Ann Arbor in 1971. The study results were processed computerized using the Microsoft Excel program. To assess the clinical evolution, was used the tabular method of forming survival curves according to Kaplan E and Meyer P.

Results

In this study, the clinical manifestations, complications and results of treatment of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma with a predominant lesion of the gastrointestinal tract were studied in 50 patients aged 20 to 78 years. By distributing patients by sex and age, it was noted that women are more often affected by this disease. For both sexes, the age of 50 to 69 years prevails, which is 64%. According to the International Clinical Classification adopted in Ann Arbor in 1971, the majority of patients - 22 people (44%) were diagnosed with stage IV of the disease. Stage II E was established in 14 (28%) patients, stage I E in 12 (24%) and stage III E in 2 (4%). note the predominance of lymphoblastic lymphomas (36 cases, or 72%). Very rare are prolymphocytic variants (2 cases, or 4%) and lymphoplasmacytic variants (1 case, or 2%). In 11 (22%) patients, the NHL variant was not detected.

The study of the morphological features of NHL with a predominant lesion of gastrointestinal tract showed that the predominant morphological variants in this group of tumors were tumors with a high degree of malignancy.

Clinical manifestations depend on the organ in which the tumor first formed. For example, with a primary lesion of the stomach, pain in the epigastric region, nausea, vomiting, belching are observed, in rare cases, vomiting of the color of "coffee grounds" is also found. In lesion of the small and large intestine - parombilical, constipation. Patients also presented symptoms of general intoxication. Most patients (76%) suffered from increased sweating, 62% had weight loss, 36% - 10% temperature.

To confirm the diagnosis, all patients underwent EGD and morphological analysis. In 20 operated patients, the material was removed during the operation. Everything else is in the process of conducting FGDS.

The effectiveness of treatment mainly depends on the stage of the disease. Thus, in stage I E, complete remission was achieved in all patients. In stage II E, the efficiency is already much lower: 43% of patients reached complete remission, 43% - partial remission, treatment was without results in 14% of cases. In the later stages (III E and IV), the treatment turned out to be ineffective already in 29% of cases. Complete remission reached 25% of patients, partial - 46%. In general, the overall effectiveness of treatment was 82.0% (remissions were achieved in 41 out of 50 patients). Of these, complete remissions were obtained in 24 (48.0%), partial - in 17 (34.0%), the effect was absent in 9 (18.0%) patients. Adverse reactions have been studied in patients receiving combined treatment (chemotherapy and radiotherapy) and drug treatment alone. The most common side effect in 34 (68.0%) patients was leukopenia. 28 (41.8%) patients had peripheral neuropathy. The appointment of antiemetic drugs did not worsen the general condition of the patients, the treatment was carried out in a standard volume and according to the scheme.

The survival time of patients with non-Hodgkin's lymphomas with a predominant lesion of the gastrointestinal tract varied from 6 to 98 months. The overall survival of patients after 1 year was 78.1%, after 3 years - 59.4% and after 5 years - 61.9%. The overall survival of patients with stage I E for 1 year was 93.4%, for 3 years - 71.4% and for 5 years - 69.9%. After the treatment, patients in stage I E were good for 1 year 93.4%,

in stage II E - 63.9%, for 3 years - 76.5% and 5 years or more - 69.9%. In stage II E, the convincing rates were 91.2%, 71.4% and 63.8%. The overall survival of patients with III E and IV stages after chemotherapy treatment was more than 1 year 75.1%, more than 3 years - 59.4% and more than 5 years - 28.5%.

Conclusion

Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas with a primary lesion of the gastrointestinal tract are a frequent extranodal manifestation of this disease, diagnosed mainly in the late stages and having aggressive forms. They occur more often at the age of 50-69 years and the female sex prevails. Treatment depends on the clinical stage of the disease; in general, remissions reach 82% of patients.

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